

BULK STRAIN SOLITONS IN POLYMERIC COMPOSITES WITH ANISODIAMETRIC INCLUSIONS

I.V. Semenova^{1*}, A.V. Belashov¹, O.A. Moskalyuk², A.M. Samsonov¹, V.E. Yudin²

¹Ioffe Institute of the RAS, Politekhnicheskaya ul., 26, St. Petersburg, 194021, Russia

²Institute of Macromolecular Compounds, Bolshoy pr. 31, St. Petersburg, 199004, Russia

*Irina.Semenova@mail.ioffe.ru

Polymeric nanocomposites are finding increasingly wide applications in areas such as aircraft engineering and automotive engineering, where components experience various dynamic loads. Rapidly growing applications of composite materials in industry stimulate analysis of various aspects of their mechanical behavior. However the composite response to intensive dynamic loading is often hard to predict since it may depend drastically upon matrix and filler characteristics, filler distribution in the matrix and on resulting mechanical characteristics of the composite.

Wave processes in general are good candidates for modeling dynamic loading of materials. Nonlinear elastic strain waves and in particular bulk strain solitary waves (solitons) may be most promising due to the anomalously low decay, stability of wave parameters in homogeneous waveguides and dependence of parameters on waveguide elasticity and geometry. Besides that these waves can be applied for measuring the third order elastic moduli of materials which are currently measured by ultrasonic technique with low accuracy.

The formation and evolution of strain solitary waves in waveguides made of pure glassy polymers (PMMA, polystyrene and polycarbonate) has been thoroughly investigated by us both experimentally and theoretically (see e.g. [1-3] and references therein). It was demonstrated that being formed such waves indeed propagate in uniform waveguides for long distances with very low attenuation. In our experiments solitons in waveguides made of the above mentioned polymers were recorded at distances up to 1 m. Soliton behavior in waveguides with different kinds of inhomogeneities including such macro-inhomogeneities as layers of glue and delamination areas was also analyzed in theory, numerical simulation and experiments (see e.g. [4-6]).

Micro- and nanostructured composites, containing a matrix and a filler, both with known physical parameters, have the characteristics, which differ considerably and often unexpectedly from those of the matrix. Considerable efforts are currently made for understanding, description and prediction of nonlinear mechanical behavior of nanocomposites. Composite materials with micro- and macro-inclusions are, in general, better developed, and their properties are more or less predictable in static experiments, while the nanostructured composites often demonstrate an unpredictable behavior, essentially in nonlinear dynamic processes.

The technology of polymeric nanocomposites is aimed at creating materials with the given properties, which are imparted by an appropriate choice of a combination of polymer matrix and filler. In this communication we present results on the development of nanocomposite materials on the base of PMMA and polystyrene matrices with different fillers, in particular SiO₂ nanoparticles and various anisodiametric inclusions: halloysite nanotubes, Mica ME-100, MMT Cloising 15A. Block samples of composite materials with different filler concentrations were obtained by melt technology (see [7] for details). An influence of the filler on thermomechanical properties of the materials was studied using dynamic mechanical analysis. The filler distribution in the polymer matrix was controlled using scanning electron microscopy. It was shown that the addition of nanoparticles to the polymer matrix leads to noticeable changes in elastic characteristics of the composite as compared to those of the pure matrix. For instance, Table 1 presents data on variations of the flexural modulus of PMMA- and polystyrene-based composites with SiO₂ nanofillers at different concentrations.

Table 1. Room-temperature flexural modulus of PMMA- and polystyrene-based nanocomposites

Polymer matrix	Flexural modulus, GPa			
	0% SiO ₂	5% SiO ₂	10% SiO ₂	20% SiO ₂
PMMA	3.69	3.92	4.11	4.89
Polystyrene	2.42	2.93	2.97	3.12

In our earlier works we showed that the possibility of generating a nonlinear strain soliton in a material is governed by a combination of its second and third-order elastic moduli, geometry of the waveguide, and parameters of an initial impact (shock wave). Thus, information about the elastic properties of the material is vital for estimating the possibility of the formation of strain solitons in it. In this communication we demonstrate and analyze experimentally the generation and propagation of strain solitons in waveguides made of produced polymeric composites. The increase/decrease of soliton velocity in materials with increased/decreased Young's modulus, respectively, is demonstrated. Variations of soliton parameters with filler concentration and aggregation are studied.

The essential limitation of our experimental approach is due to recording of wave processes in transmission configuration, and, as a result, impossibility to study opaque samples. For potential applications any other technology providing accurate measurements of soliton amplitude and velocity may be applied but for research purposes wave 'visualization' is preferable. To accomplish that, we have recently developed a method for indirect monitoring of strain solitons in opaque (composite) materials that allows us to investigate almost any material providing soliton formation [8]. The method is based on the inspection of a two-layered waveguide, composed of a layer, made of an opaque material (e.g. composite), and another one made of transparent material (e.g. a pure polymer matrix), bonded by a glasslike adhesive. In the bonded area of the waveguide with layers made of different materials the single generalized soliton is formed propagating in the layered structure as a unified entity. Then the soliton parameters in an opaque waveguide are determined based on the soliton parameters in a transparent one. Measurements of soliton parameters - amplitude, full width at half maximum, velocity – in the transparent layer thus provide data for determination of the dynamic elastic characteristics of the composite material.

The results obtained may be of use for estimation of operational stability of functional and structural components made of reinforced polymeric composites. The possibility of strain soliton generation in different structures, especially in those used in important branches of industry, such as aerospace engineering and oil and gas transportation, should be taken into consideration.

References

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